

CULTURAL DEVELOPMENT AND ITS IMPACT ON YOUNG PEOPLE

Melikova Martaba Numonovna
Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages,
Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor,
Head of the Department of Humanities and
Information Technology
E-mail: martabamelikova@gmail.com

Annotation. The article is devoted to the study of the influence of culture on the youth of Asia in the context of globalization and technological progress. Traditional values, the influence of modern technologies, as well as the issues of preserving national identity among young people are considered.

Key words: youth, culture, Asia, globalization, traditions, identity, technology.

Culture plays a key role in shaping young people's identities, defining their values, norms, and lifestyles. Asia, as a region with a rich historical heritage and a variety of cultural traditions, is a unique example of the interaction of tradition and modernity in the lives of young people. This article examines the main trends in cultural change among Asian youth, the impact of globalization and digital technologies, and the preservation of national identity.

The issues of the influence of culture on young people and the transformation of national identity in the context of globalization are widely considered in scientific works. S. Huntington in his work "The Clash of Civilizations" (1996) emphasizes the importance of cultural identities in world processes and their impact on youth communities. Z. Bauman in his book "Globalization. Consequences for the individual and society" (2000) analyzes changes in traditional societies and the adaptation of young people to new realities.

Robertson's work "Globalization: Social Theories and Global Culture" (2003) explores the balance between globalization and local cultural practices. Hofstede in "The Dimension of Cultures" (2001) examines in detail the influence of national values on the formation of personality. These works provide an important theoretical basis for studying changes in the culture and self-consciousness of Asian youth.

Many societies are traditionally oriented towards collectivism, respect for the elderly, family foundations and spiritual practices. In countries such as China, Japan, South Korea, and India, these values are passed down from generation to generation.

Confucianism, Buddhism, Islam, and Hinduism continue to play an important role in shaping young people's worldviews, influencing their behavior, moral norms, and social relationships.

With the spread of the internet and social media, young people in Asia are increasingly influenced by Western culture. The popularity of K-pop, anime, online games, and international brands is shaping a new lifestyle based on global trends. However, Asian youth are adapting these elements by combining them with local traditions. For example, the South Korean wave (Hallyu) shows how Asian culture can integrate into the world cultural space while preserving its identity.

The cultural changes brought about by globalization have had a significant impact on the national identity of young people in Asia. On the one hand, the active borrowing of elements of Western culture contributes to the development of intercultural dialogue and integration into the global community. On the other hand, there is a danger of losing national traditions and languages, which causes concern among the older generation and cultural figures.

Many young Asians are in the process of searching for identity, combining elements of traditional culture with modern trends. In countries such as China, Japan and South Korea, a new patriotism is developing, which is expressed in the popularization of national art, fashion and language. Government initiatives aimed at strengthening national identity include educational programmes, support for national films and music, and cultural festivals.

The transformation of culture in the context of globalization does not lead to a complete blurring of national identity, but rather contributes to its adaptation to new conditions, providing young people with the opportunity to express themselves and preserve cultural heritage. Despite the impact of globalization, many Asian countries are taking measures to preserve national culture. In China and Japan, interest in traditional arts such as calligraphy, tea ceremonies and martial arts is developing. In Southeast Asian countries, folk festivals and ceremonies are supported, attracting young people to participate in cultural traditions.

Young people in Asia are in a unique position between ancient traditions and modern trends. Globalization and technological innovation bring new forms of expression, but cultural identity remains an important part of their lives. It is important to find a balance between preserving traditions and integrating into the global community, which will allow the youth of Asia to develop in harmony with the historical heritage of their countries.

References

1. Huntington S. Clash of Civilizations and the Transformation of the World Order. Moscow, AST Publ., 1996.
2. Bauman Z. Globalization. Consequences for the individual and society. Moscow, Ves mir Publ., 2000.
3. Inglehart R. Cultural Change in Modern Societies. Moscow, Novoe izdatelstvo Publ., 2003.
4. Robertson R. Globalization: Social Theories and Global Culture. Moscow, Aspect Press Publ., 2003.
5. Hofstede G. Dimension of Cultures: International Studies of Values and Behavior. Moscow, Vysshaya shkola ekonomiki Publ., 2001.